

Problems and prospects in the development of public administration of scientific research activities in higher education institutions

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Abstract. This article discusses the problems of managing the research activities of university students showed that the study of its theoretical and practical aspects. In my opinion, this development can occur by constructing and using the structural-functional model of managing the research activities of university students.

The history and theory of pedagogy indicate that purposefully organized process of human education was built and built on different grounds, has different goals and ways of their realization. It is expressed both in different forms of specific pedagogical actions and attitudes, and in many pedagogical systems, concepts, theories, technologies and techniques. Attempts to systematically comprehend them are inextricably linked to the development of conceptual models of education of varying degrees of community, which act as special ideal objects.

Management of student research activities is seen as a complex system consisting of certain interrelated elements: the target; management principles, functions and methods; structural components of students' research activities; meaningful; technological and productive.

The goal is to achieve the intended result. The purpose of the model of management of research activity of students of the university is formation of competence of students in research activity.

In our study, the concept of competence is defined as the ability and willingness to apply knowledge and skills in solving professional problems in various fields of science. Competence involves the presence of cognitive abilities (understanding and use of ideas and thoughts), methodological abilities (organizing time, decision making or problem solving), the desire for self-development and self-improvement. The concept of "competence" appears in this case as a result of purposeful, systematic activity in the management of research activities of university students.

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The stated goal defines the content and pedagogical conditions that allow to predict the expected result, as well as sets the guidelines for the activity of the university teachers.

Management of research activities of university students is a complex step-by-step process, which depends on the organization of the appropriate conditions under which we mean the ways, means, forms and methods of organizing research activities.

As organizational and pedagogical conditions, we propose:

- Organization of the school of a young researcher;
- Student self-government and joint management, the activities of teachers and students in managing the activities of the scientific community.

Efficiency of functioning depends on the degree of implementation of the principles by which it operates. As you know, the principle is the basic idea of any activity, the basic rule of behavior of the subject. In the implementation of the model, the principles reflect the requirements of objective laws and are the most general rules in which the basic needs of its functioning and development are expressed in awareness.

The problem of management principles is widely covered in philosophical, sociological, psychological and pedagogical literature. However, the question of which principles should be highlighted and how to classify them is still debatable.

Thus, S. I. Arkhangelsky distinguishes the following principles: weak link, change of equilibrium, insufficient information and strong basis. Essential for management, as the author points out, is the hierarchical principle, conducting control, analysis, synthesis of information, making adjustments at different levels of management [4].

According to Yu. A. Konarzhevsky, the principles of management of higher education institutions are based on such principles as democratic centralism, unity, subordination to the management of a political task, planning, which expresses the initiative of the leader, objectivity and science, concreteness, the principle of the leading link, flexibility and latitude of maneuver, stimulation, combination of interests of personality and collective, correct selection and rational placement of personnel [3].

These principles have both scientific and applied value, and play a significant role in the organization of the educational process. At the same time, the political, economic and cultural factors influencing the education system make it possible to identify other principles that must be taken into account.

The model of managing research activities of students of higher educational institutions is based on the principles of dialogism, gradualness, coordination, integration,

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unity of management and self-government. The principles are the starting points that guide the entire process of implementing the proposed theory.

The basis of students' research activities is the pedagogical interaction between the teacher and the student. In the implementation, which is a dialectic chain of diverse and diverse pedagogical phenomena arises in all areas of students' activities. The formation of the personality of a future specialist occurs under the influence of the surrounding social environment and the relationships that are established in it with teachers and students. In this regard, the principle of dialogism plays an important role in the organization of students' research activities. Three types of relationships are distinguished: 1) the relationship between objects, 2) the relationship between the subject and the object, 3) the relationship between the subjects - personal, personal relationships: dialogic relationships, ethical relationships. The principle of dialogism is based on the fact that only in the conditions of subjective relations, equal cooperation and interaction is it possible to form the personality of a future specialist.

The principle of dialogism is aimed, first of all, at subjective relations, to personalize the interaction of the teacher and student. This principle rejects the ranking position of the student, turns him into a partner who independently acquires knowledge.

Considering the management of students' research activities in the structure of higher education, it should be noted that the relationship between its stages is so "multifaceted" that knowledge of the features of only one of the stages does not give a complete picture of it. To create a scientifically based theory of managing research activities of students, it is necessary to identify the continuity of the stages of higher education.

By continuity is understood the connection between phenomena in the development process, when the new, replacing the old, retains some of its elements. Continuity is considered as the principle of functioning of all managed social systems. Without which the progressive development of society is impossible. The fundamental significance of continuity is that it provides a link between the past, present and future. Continuity is of an objective and general nature, manifests itself in all spheres of public life and provides for the transfer of cultural values and norms of social behavior from one generation to another. The assimilation of values and norms by one generation creates the prerequisite for the subsequent creation of new values and norms for new generations.

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The principle of continuity involves the enrichment of means, forms and methods of training, accumulates positive results at all stages of students' research activities. Continuity determines the nature of the relationship between the elements of students' research activities, helps to establish patterns, allows us to assume the logic of further development.

In the process of student's succession, the formation of individual elements and concepts into a logical system of knowledge takes place. Continuity consists not only in the preservation and transformation of knowledge, skills from one stage to another, but also in their classification, the emergence of new knowledge and the development of forms and methods of training are provided. In the research activities of students, the principle of heredity is manifested in the transition of a student from one general educational level to another, higher, which makes it possible for the further development of the student's personality.

The principle of coordination reflects the methods of action of management entities aimed at coordinated work. He aims to study and consciously use the features of the mechanism of interaction of management subjects in the achievement of the priority goals of students' research activities.

The role of coordination is to find the optimal ratio between the actions of the subject and the control object. Coordination creates the conditions for sequential actions of the subject and the control object, involves the correlation of goals, resources, forms and methods of activity and leads to a common result.

The principle of the unity of management and self-government in the research activities of students is that as democratic processes develop, changes occur not only in their content and forms, but also in the relationship between them. The essence of self-government cannot be investigated in isolation from management mechanisms. Management and self-government should be considered in moments of unity and difference. Management and self-government act as a union of opposites that imply each other. Hence, the effective management in the institution of higher education, the faster and more fully develops self-government. The effectiveness of management, in turn, grows with the development of self-government and, thus, enrichment of one form of activity of another takes place.

The principle of integration allows us to ensure the connection of acquired knowledge, skills of research activities in the educational process by strengthening the links between the content, means and forms of training. Integration leads to the strengthening of

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the universality of the elements of the educational process and the harmonization of the relationships between them, contributes to their integration.

Planning is one of the components of the management of students research activities, is based on analysis, consists in the development and practical implementation of plans, methods, means of achieving goals.

Organization is the process of establishing a certain order necessary for the effective functioning of students' research activities, combining the activities of all structures of higher education institutions in accordance with the goals. Organization of students' research activities is the balancing of all types of resources (intellectual, technical, financial), their integration into the complex process of creating a functional pedagogical system.

Thus, we found that the management of students research activities in modern sociocultural conditions should be considered as a focused interaction of management subjects, ensuring the formation of students' competence in research activities and its transfer to a higher, high-quality state. Under its management, the political, economic and cultural factors of social development are updated, which act as incentives for the improvement of personality. Such a model of managing the research activities of university students as the main elements provides: the purpose, principles, functions and management methods; structural components of research activities; content; implementation technology and its result. The functioning of the model is based on the principles of dialogism, heredity, coordination, integration and unity of management and self-government.s.

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